

Evaluation of Spectral Estimation Parameters for Direct Sampling FFT-based Measuring Receivers

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ABSTRACT The standard CISPR 16-1-1 defines the measuring receiver using a black-box approach and sets requirements for its accuracy and spectral properties. Traditionally, such test receivers were developed using a superheterodyne architecture. Recently, time-domain electromagnetic emission measurement systems have been built employing direct sampling instruments, mainly oscilloscopes, and relying on specific signal processing to emulate the performance of compliant instruments. In these cases, the short-time Fourier transform is used for spectral estimation, but the corresponding electromagnetic compatibility standards lack details for its correct use with respect to parameters such as windowing function, overlapping factor, and frequency interpolation. Moreover, it is unclear which combination of spectral estimation parameters is best fit for this purpose. Obtaining reliable, consistent and low uncertainty spectral estimates of electromagnetic emissions measured in time-domain needs appropriate configuration and tuning of the signal processing algorithms. This paper investigates the error in the calculated spectrum for various reference signals: multitone, chirp pulses and rectangular pulses. The analysis is carried out for each CISPR band from A to D, that is, between 9 kHz and 1 GHz. After 489.6×10^3 iterations, distributed in 1700 different digital implementations of the CISPR 16-1-1 measuring receiver, the simulations outcomes point to certain sets of parameters that showed satisfactory performance overall, being the Nutall, Kaiser, and Parzen windows with more than 75% of overlapping and using interpolation factor higher than 5, generally suitable. Calibration results are used to experimentally verify that a valid set of parameters is adequate to fulfil CISPR 16-1-1 requirements.

INDEX TERMS CISPR-16-1-1, electromagnetic compatibility, measuring receiver, short-time Fourier Transform, standards, time-domain measurements.

I. INTRODUCTION

ELECTROMAGNETIC Compatibility (EMC) is the ability of a system to work as intended in a given electromagnetic environment and without interfering with radiocommunications or other devices installed in the surroundings [1]. Unintentional radiofrequency (RF) emissions must be controlled to ensure EMC. Typically, assessing the conducted and radiated electromagnetic emissions produced by electronic apparatus or installations

involves performing spectrum measurements and checking the detected disturbance levels with respect to limits established in EMC standards. For that purpose, the measuring receiver constitutes the essential instrument in the test setup used to evaluate electromagnetic interference (EMI).

According to the terms found in the standard CISPR 16-1-1 Ed. 5.0 (2019) [2] of the Comité International Spécial des Perturbations Radioélectriques (CISPR), a

measuring receiver is defined as an “*instrument such as a tunable voltmeter, an EMI receiver, a spectrum analyzer, or a Fast Fourier Transform (FFT)-based measuring instrument, with or without preselection, which meets the relevant parts of this standard*”. Consequently, CISPR 16-1-1 does not provide specific guidelines for the implementation of a measuring receiver; instead, it lays out a set of requirements that the instrument must satisfy within a black-box framework. These prerequisites, focused on the baseline criteria, encompass five key parameters: impedance matching at the instrument input port, sine-wave voltage tolerance, overall pass-band selectivity, response to pulses and frequency tuning tolerance [3].

One of the fundamental distinctions in the functioning of measuring receivers is the choice between the frequency-swept method with a superheterodyne architecture and those based on time-domain implementations, also known as FFT-based receivers. While the frequency-swept approach has been widely employed in emissions testing for decades, time domain-based techniques have gained relevance due to their speed and capability to capture transient disturbances, short-duration events that are often missed by their frequency-domain counterparts [4], [5].

The advantages of time-domain techniques and the wide availability of general-purpose instruments capable of sampling RF signals in real-time with sufficient dynamic range and accuracy have resulted in ad-hoc FFT-based receiver implementations for evaluating EMI in complex scenarios. Examples can be found using oscilloscopes [6]–[8], wideband real-time architectures [9] and modal receivers [10]. In all cases, the signal processing required to deliver the measurement output involves several steps, namely, resolution enhancement, filtering, spectral estimation, detector emulation, and the application of correction factors. Hence, designing the instrument’s processing chain is crucial to meet standard requirements.

Spectral estimation, particularly through the Short-Time Fourier Transform (STFT), is therefore pivotal to FFT-based measuring receivers. The STFT has been extensively applied to estimate the spectrum of signals, allowing the identification of frequency components within a time-varying signal. Essential parameters in STFT configuration include window function, overlapping factor, and frequency interpolation method. As these parameters influence the quality of spectral estimation, their rigorous selection and configuration are key for minimizing spectral errors, ensuring the accuracy of measurements, as shown in [11] for the case of supraharmonic disturbances.

However, there is little information on EMC standards concerning the abovementioned points. The lack of guidelines may affect the quality of the measurement, increasing the measurement uncertainty and leading to unintended errors or causing divergences between results obtained from different implementations of FFT-based

measuring receivers. Previous research supports this statement. For instance, in [12], the suitability of the CISPR 16 method for measuring conducted emissions in the 2 kHz–150 kHz range in low voltage grids was investigated, concluding that digital implementations of the measuring receiver by CISPR 16-1-1 are not properly defined, compromising the comparability of emissions test results even when using compliant instruments.

To fill that void, this paper investigates the spectral estimation parameters for direct sampling FFT-based measuring receivers, with the objective of evaluating their impact on the spectrum level error. With respect to [12], this paper expands the frequency range up to 1 GHz and covers not only the quasi-peak (QP) detector but also the peak (PK), average (AVE) and root-mean-square (RMS) detectors. Moreover, the results are obtained through simulations comprising digital implementations of measuring receivers and synthetic signals, and the optimized receiver implementation was validated in calibration conditions using metrology-class references.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows. Section II overviews the fundamentals of spectral estimation for EMI measurements in time-domain. Subsequently, Section III presents the methodology and the rationale for selecting reference signals and key parameters involved in the study. Then, Section IV and V show the results for every parameter evaluated and their experimental validation through traceable calibration results. The article ends with the conclusions for each numerical experiment and gathers a set of global parameters recommended for fitting the signal processing to EMC standard requirements.

II. SPECTRAL ESTIMATION FOR EMI MEASUREMENTS

A continuous-time signal function, $x(t)$, that represents the measured EMI is observed during a time period of length T_0 . In order to computationally evaluate the frequency spectrum of $x(t)$, $X(f)$, the measured signal is sampled and digitized to obtain a time-discrete signal, $x[n]$, where n is an integer and $x[n]$ is assumed as periodic with the total number of samples, N , that is, $x[n + N] = x[n]$. Therefore,

$$x[n] = x(n\Delta t) \quad (1)$$

where $T_0 = N\Delta t$ and Δt is the sampling interval, that is, $\Delta t = 1/f_s$, f_s being the sampling frequency. It is understood that f_s at least fulfills the Nyquist-Shannon criteria. Moreover, as a rule of thumb, if the maximum measurable frequency is f_{\max} it is recommended to use $f_s \geq 4f_{\max}$ in order to avoid undesired aliasing errors. Then, the discrete frequency spectrum $X[k]$ is related to the continuous frequency spectrum $X(f)$ by

$$X[k] = X(k\Delta f), \quad (2)$$

where k is integer and Δf is the spacing of the spectral lines. The quantities N , T_0 , Δt , and Δf are related by

$$\Delta f = \frac{N}{T_0}. \quad (3)$$

The Discrete Fourier Transform (DFT) is given by

$$X[k] = \sum_{n=0}^{N-1} x[n] e^{-j \frac{2\pi nk}{N}}. \quad (4)$$

The spectral estimation is performed based on the DFT, assuming that the $x[n]$ is periodic in n with a period N . However, $x[n]$ is not necessarily periodic since there is only a single continuously measured signal sequence of length N .

Therefore, to reduce the scalloping loss and the spectral leakage caused by its finite length, the time record $x[n]$ is multiplied by a window function $w[n]$ which exhibits a maximum value for $n = N/2$ and smoothly goes to zero for n approaching 0 or $N - 1$, respectively [13], [14],

$$x_w[n] = x[n]w[n], \quad (5)$$

where $x_w[n]$ is the windowed signal in the discrete-time domain. Consequently, in the frequency domain, this yields a convolution, which is given by,

$$X_w[k] = X[k] * W[k] = \sum_{m=0}^{N-1} X[m]W[k-m]. \quad (6)$$

If windowing is used, it is necessary to compensate for the energy loss caused by the window using the coherent gain scaling factor, G_C [15], which is defined as,

$$G_C = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{n=0}^{N-1} w[n]. \quad (7)$$

Furthermore, calculating the spectrum for a specific equivalent resolution bandwidth (RBW), requires a minimum number of samples in the time record, that is,

$$N_{\min} = f_s \left(\frac{w_f}{\text{RBW}} \right), \quad (8)$$

where w_f is a constant factor equal to the window bandwidth in frequency bins at a given cut-off level, usually -6 dB [6].

In addition, if $N > N_{\min}$, it is possible to define $M > 1$ overlapping windows, each of them of length equal to N_{\min} , in order to determine the frequency and phase content of the m -th local sections of an EMI signal as it changes over time. This process is called the Short-Time Fourier Transform (STFT) and it is given by,

$$X_m[k] = \sum_{n=0}^{N_{\min}-1} x[n]w[n-m(1-o_f)N_{\min}] e^{-j \frac{2\pi nk}{N_{\min}}}, \quad (9)$$

where o_f is the overlap factor (generally between 0.5 and 0.95) and $m = 0, 1, 2, \dots, (M-1)$ is the time shift index that controls the sliding of the overlapping window between successive time frames.

Besides, since EMI measurement time is usually larger than the minimum, N_{\min}/f_s , it is possible to apply non-parametric spectral estimation techniques based on the periodogram. This is convenient for improving the accuracy and precision of the amplitude spectrum of stationary random signals by means of the reduction of the spectrum variance achieved through averaging on the frequency domain [16].

The periodogram method was first published by Bartlett [17]. In Bartlett's method, the data is smoothed by averaging over the power computed for a number M of short-time signal segments. Later, Welch combined DFT methods using window functions and developed a method for averaging short, modified periodograms [18].

As stated before, both periodogram methods, Bartlett- and Welch-, are based on the averaging of the spectra obtained by applying the STFT to the time-domain EMI signal. In the Bartlett method, the time domain sequence is subdivided into P non-overlapping segments, where each segment has length N_{\min} . For each segment, the periodogram is computed and the Bartlett power spectral estimate is obtained by averaging the periodograms for the segments. Then, the frequency spectrum calculated by the Bartlett periodogram [19] is given by,

$$P_B[k] = \frac{1}{PN_{\min}} \sum_{p=0}^{P-1} \left| \sum_{n=0}^{N_{\min}-1} x[n+mN_{\min}] e^{-j \frac{2\pi nk}{N_{\min}}} \right|^2. \quad (10)$$

By this averaging of the spectrum, the variance of the spectrum estimation is reduced by a factor M , however, at the expense of a reduction of the frequency resolution by the same factor [16]. Welch [18] modified Bartlett's method by using windowed data segments overlapping in time. The windowing is applied to reduce the spectral leakage associated with finite observation intervals. The overlapping time windows yield a further reduction of the periodogram variance. The frequency spectrum calculated by Welch's periodogram [13] is given by

$$P_W[k] = \frac{1}{MN_{\min}W} \sum_{m=0}^{M-1} |X_m[k]|^2, \quad (11)$$

where W is the discrete-time window gain, given by,

$$W = \frac{1}{N_{\min}} \sum_{n=0}^{N_{\min}-1} w^2[n]. \quad (12)$$

Equation (9) provides the information about the time-frequency distribution of $x(t)$, $X_m[k]$ can be used for calculating the single-sided amplitude spectrum, $S_A[k, m]$, corresponding to the different detector modes required for standard EMI measurements [20]–[22]. Accordingly,

$$S_A[k, m] = \begin{cases} \frac{|X_m[0]|}{N_{\min}G_C} & \text{for } k = 0 \\ \frac{\sqrt{2}|X_m[k]|}{N_{\min}G_C} & \text{for } 1 \leq k < k_{\text{Nyquist}} \end{cases} \quad (13)$$

where the discrete Nyquist frequency, k_{Nyquist} , is given by

$$k_{\text{Nyquist}} = \begin{cases} N_{\min}/2 & \text{for even } N_{\min} \\ (N_{\min} + 1)/2 & \text{for odd } N_{\min} \end{cases} \quad (14)$$

Equation (13) considers only the spectral amplitudes up to the Nyquist frequency. For negative frequencies, the respective spectral amplitudes are conjugate complex of ones on the positive side of the spectrum. Then, the single side spectrum corresponds to twice the spectral amplitudes

in the region $1 \leq k < k_{\text{Nyquist}}$ and the expression is divided by $\sqrt{2}$ to account for the effective value.

Subsequently, in the particular case of the peak detector, $S_{\text{pk}}[k]$, it corresponds to,

$$S_{\text{pk}}[k] = \max \{|S_A[k, m]| \text{ for } m \in [0, M-1]\}. \quad (15)$$

Likewise, the corresponding expressions for the average and the RMS detectors are given by,

$$S_{\text{ave}}[k] = \frac{1}{M} \sum_{m=0}^{M-1} S_A[k, m], \text{ and}, \quad (16)$$

$$S_{\text{rms}}[k] = \sqrt{\frac{1}{M} \sum_{m=0}^{M-1} S_A^2[k, m]}, \quad (17)$$

respectively.

Finally, regarding the QP detector, $S_{\text{qp}}[k]$, it is emulated by applying a weighting correction factor for each frequency bin that is a function of the equivalent pulse repetition frequency (PRF). In that sense, the equivalent PRF is calculated by inverting the pulse response curves defined in the CISPR 16-1-1 standard and using the measured $S_{\text{pk}}[k]/S_{\text{ave}}[k]$ and $S_{\text{pk}}[k]/S_{\text{rms}}[k]$ ratios. The amplitude relationship for detectors must obey the following condition:

$$S_{\text{pk}}[k] \geq S_{\text{qp}}[k] \geq S_{\text{rms}}[k] \geq S_{\text{ave}}[k]. \quad (18)$$

III. METHODOLOGY

A set of simulations are performed to study the accuracy of the EMI spectrum estimation algorithms according to their configuration parameters. There, reference signals with known and controlled spectral properties are generated numerically and then applied to the functions that implement the calculations explained in Section II. From the spectral estimates obtained, we determine the error associated with the different sets of parameters with respect to the expected values. Below, we explain the spectral estimation parameters considered in this study.

A. Spectral estimation parameters

The parameters under evaluation are the type of windowing function, the window overlapping factor, and the spectrum interpolation factor. The simulations are run and processed using MATLAB code.

Overlapping factor, α_f : The term overlapping factor refers to how much superposition there is between adjacent time windows of the signal. For this study, we have worked with overlapping factors from 50% to 95% in steps of 5%.

Types of windowing functions: Seventeen different functions are considered, and they are: Bartlett, modified Bartlett-Hann, Blackman, Blackman-Harris, Bohman, Chebyshev (sidelobe attenuation, $r = 100$ dB), Flat-Top, Gaussian (width factor, $\alpha = 2.5$), Hamming, Hann, Kaiser-Bessel (shape factor, $\beta = 16.7$), Nuttall, Parzen, rectangular, Taylor, triangular and Tukey (cosine fraction, $r = 0.5$). Window length is given by (8).

Spectrum interpolation factor, F_{int} : Interpolation can be used to increase the density of points of the calculated spectrum without changing the resolution bandwidth. Therefore, the spectrum interpolation factor is the number of equidistant frequency points estimated between the ends of an original frequency step. The frequency step of the STFT was fixed to $1/4$ RBW, and then spectrum interpolation factors were configured from 1 to 10.

B. Reference signals

The reference signals have been designed to exercise the spectral estimation algorithms in a meaningful way from an EMC perspective. Therefore, they comprise typical characteristics of narrowband and broadband EMI. Also, each reference signal has variations for the different CISPR bands, from A to C/D. Table 1 summarizes the common parameters for generating the reference signals for each frequency range. A description of the reference signals is provided in what follows.

TABLE 1. General setting for generating the reference signals.

CISPR Band	Freq. range	f_s	Period
A	9 kHz-150 kHz	1 MSa/s	1 s
B	150 kHz-30 MHz	125 MSa/s	100 ms
C/D	30 MHz-1 GHz	2.5 GSa/s	10 ms

Reference Signal 1 - Multitone: Multitone signals produce a spectrum similar to one from high harmonic content EMI sources, e.g. switching noise from power converters or high-speed digital signals. This type of reference signal can simultaneously excite an entire frequency range. It is important to generate a multitone signal with minimal leakage, then it is mandatory to choose a combination of tones with an integer number of periods within the reference waveform vector. Likewise, reducing dynamic range compression effects by lowering the multitone signal crest factor is desirable. This is possible by appropriately selecting the relative phases of the individual tones, according to the criterion in [23].

Table 2 summarizes the properties of this reference signal including the lower and upper frequencies of the tones, f_l and f_u ; the distance between adjacent tones, Δf ; the total number of tones, N_{tones} ; and the quasi-peak level, S_{qp} .

TABLE 2. Parameters of the reference signal 1 - Multitone.

Band	f_l	f_u	Δf	N_{tones}	S_{qp}
A	10 kHz	150 kHz	5 kHz	28	60 dB μ V
B	200 kHz	29.9 MHz	300 kHz	99	60 dB μ V
C/D	30 MHz	1 GHz	19.4 MHz	50	60 dB μ V

As an example, Fig. 1 shows the spectrum of Band B multitone reference signal. It is important to note that for this reference signal, no difference in the spectrum level of the peaks of the tones is expected from the weighting detectors.

FIGURE 1. Spectrum of the reference signal 1 - Multitone for CISPR Band B and according to the parameters specified in Table 2.

Reference Signal 2 - Chirp: Chirp signals are commonly found in sources of intentional EMI, like jammers. They have similar properties to emissions sources where spread spectrum techniques are used. In our case, reference signal 2 is defined as a linear and monotonically increasing chirp. Table 3 gathers the properties of this reference signal, including the start and end frequencies of the chirp, f_l and f_u ; the chirp sweep time, ΔT ; and the quasi-peak spectrum level, S_{qp} .

TABLE 3. Parameters of the reference signal 2: Chirp.

Band	f_l	f_u	ΔT	S_{qp}
A	50 kHz	100 kHz	40 ms	60 dB μ V
B	10 MHz	20 MHz	10 ms	60 dB μ V
C/D	50 MHz	100 MHz	10 ms	60 dB μ V

Fig. 2 shows the spectrum of the chirp reference signal in CISPR Band B. PK, QP, AVE and RMS detectors are shown. The weighting detectors provide different readings depending on the pulse repetition frequency, $f_{rep} = 1/\Delta T$. In all cases, the chirp sweep time is selected such that f_{rep} is as indicated in the CISPR 16-1-1 standard for the absolute pulse response calibration.

FIGURE 2. Spectrum of the reference signal 2 - Chirp for CISPR Band B and according to the parameters specified in Table 3.

Reference Signal 3 - Rectangular pulse: The last reference signal consists of a periodic rectangular pulse

that emulates the one used for standard calibration of the response to pulses of the receiver [24]. The said pulses have a short duration and fast rise time, producing an approximately flat frequency spectrum in the corresponding frequency range. Moreover, the bandwidth of the pulses spans beyond the maximum frequency of the said CISPR band [25]. Table 4 contains the specifications of this reference signal including the pulse width, t_w ; the pulse area in open circuit conditions, A ; the pulse repetition frequency, f_{rep} ; and the QP spectrum level, S_{qp} , as measured by a 50Ω matched instrument.

TABLE 4. Parameters of the reference signal 3: Rectangular pulse.

Band	t_w	A	f_{rep}	S_{qp}
A	10 μ s	13.5 μ Vs	25 Hz	60 dB μ V
B	10 ns	0.316 μ Vs	100 Hz	60 dB μ V
C/D	300 ps	0.044 μ Vs	100 Hz	60 dB μ V

Fig. 3 depicts the spectrum of the reference rectangular pulse in CISPR Band B. As in the previous case, the weighting detectors provide readings as a function of f_{rep} .

FIGURE 3. Spectrum of the reference signal 3 - Rectangular pulses for CISPR Band B and according to the parameters specified in Table 4.

C. Simulations

Considering all possible combinations of signal processing parameters, reference signals, standard detector functions, and CISPR bands, the total amount of combinations arising for the numerical experiment is 489.6×10^3 , distributed in 1700 different digital versions of the CISPR 16-1-1 receiver. To run the calculations on such a large number of variations, we developed a program that processes the reference signals as a fully compliant measuring receiver would. The said program executes according to the flowchart in Fig. 4

The simulation starts by generating a certain reference signal according to the general settings in Table 1 for a given CISPR band. Likewise, a set of parameters is chosen for the spectral estimation. Next, the generated signal is transformed to the frequency domain following the procedure described in Section II. The error in the spectral

FIGURE 4. Simplified representation of the numerical simulation scheme through a flowchart.

estimation is calculated for each detector function as the difference between the theoretically expected amplitude level and the one obtained from the simulation at the frequencies of injection. The expected amplitude level is fixed for the QP detector, while for other detector functions the reference level is calculated using the ratios defined in CISPR 16-1-1 for the reference pulse repetition frequency corresponding to each CISPR band. We used double-precision floating-point format on all calculations, and neither rounding nor truncation was made in data. Therefore, it was considered that the computational uncertainty in the reference signals is negligible. After the calculations are completed for a single case, the process is repeated for a different reference signal and/or sets of spectral estimation parameters. Once the whole space of possible combinations has been solved, the results are explored and analyzed as a whole taking into account the distribution of the errors obtained.

IV. RESULTS

In this section, we report the results of the simulations performed, presenting the outcomes per parameter and reference signal. Due to paper length constraints and for the sake of clarity, only the most relevant outputs are presented. All the result files are available upon request.

A. Overlapping factor

As expected, a noticeable difference is found between reference signals when it comes to the error resulting from different overlapping factors. The spectrum of multitone signals is estimated with negligible error even without overlapping as shown in Fig. 5. In this case, the distribution of the error barely changes when sweeping over σ_f .

Contrarily, for reference signal 2, the error is drastically reduced when the overlapping factor increases, as depicted

FIGURE 5. Overlapping factor versus amplitude error. Kaiser-Bessel window, QP detector, Band A and reference signal 1.

in the example shown in Fig. 6. From the results, it is observed that, in most cases, an overlapping factor of at least 75% was required to make the amplitude error less than 0.1 dB. This behaviour is even more critical for reference signal 3, where using high overlapping factors, $\sigma_f \geq 0.5$ is mandatory to avoid aberrant outcomes. However, higher overlapping factors will result in longer processing time and larger memory requirements.

FIGURE 6. Overlapping factor versus amplitude error. Kaiser-Bessel window, QP detector, Band B and reference signal 2.

For reference signal 3, the error behaviour as a function of σ_f is similar for most bell-shaped windows. This is convenient because it minimizes the error contributions due to the actual window shape, isolating the overlapping factor effect in the error. Also, it allows for reducing the number of different windowing functions required to analyze the influence of the overlapping factor further, making the interpretation of the results less complicated. Then, we selected the two best window functions to display the results. In that sense, a box plot is used to select such windows, as shown in Fig. 7 for Band A. The errors are compared for each type of window in the $0.5 \leq \sigma_f \leq 0.95$ range. In the plot below, one relevant insight is that the lower the error variability is for a window, the less sensitive the spectrum is to overlapping factor changes. This is an important aspect to consider due to overlapping factor impact on the computational cost.

FIGURE 7. Amplitude error per type of window for $0.5 \leq \alpha_f \leq 0.95$ for Band A and reference signal 3.

The window functions that resulted in lower amplitude errors are the Kaiser-Bessel and the Parzen ones. Using the said windowing functions, the error is investigated in the same range of α_f but now using a finer step size of 0.1%. The results are shown in Fig. 8. The similarity in the performance of Kaiser-Bessel and Parzen windows is confirmed, and even if, for most overlapping factors, the spectrum amplitude error is small, it is still possible to obtain large errors when impulsive signals coincide with the crossing point of adjacent windows. The location of that exact critical instant depends on the window shape and length. Therefore, the peaks in Fig. 8 seem shifted even if the reference signal is the same. In both cases, an $\alpha_f \geq 0.75$ is necessary to prevent outliers.

FIGURE 8. Comparison of Kaiser-Bessel and Parzen windows amplitude error as a function of the overlapping factor. QP detector, Band A and reference signal 3.

In practice, electromagnetic disturbances are typically not perfectly periodic. So, we repeated the simulations, adding some small jitter to the reference signal ($\pm 0.1\%$ of the period). As the overlapping factor increases, the amplitude error asymptotically decreases to 0 dB without arising aberrant values. The results are depicted in Fig. 9.

FIGURE 9. Amplitude error per window function and overlapping factors. QP detector, Band A and for the jittered reference signal 3.

B. Windowing function

The amplitude error produced by the windowing functions is analyzed for all reference signals, using box plots to represent the error distribution. For reference signal 1, the overlapping factor is kept at 95%. During the first inspection, Taylor and modified Bartlett-Hann windows resulted in significantly higher errors. Consequently, the said window functions are removed from the plots concerning the multitone. Fig. 10 to Fig. 12 show the window functions with the best performance for reference signal 1 inside a green shaded area (± 0.015 dB).

FIGURE 10. Error distribution per window function. QP detector, $\alpha_f = 0.95$, Band A and reference signal 1.

FIGURE 11. Error distribution per window function. QP detector, $\alpha_f = 0.95$, Band B and reference signal 1.

FIGURE 12. Error distribution per window function. QP detector, $\sigma_f = 0.95$, Band C/D and reference signal 1.

For reference signals 2 and 3, the variability in the error is mainly because of the overlapping factor while frequency variations are less important since both reference signals provide a flat response in their intended frequency range. For this reason, the box plots shown in Fig. 13 to Fig. 18 gather the data from all the iterations of the overlapping factor per each window function. The best window functions are those which are less sensitive to the changes in σ_f and are highlighted in bold as they fall in the green shaded band (± 0.05 dB).

FIGURE 13. Error distribution per window function. QP detector, Band A and reference signal 2.

FIGURE 14. Error distribution per window function. QP detector, Band B and reference signal 2.

FIGURE 15. Error distribution per window function. QP detector, Band C/D and reference signal 2.

FIGURE 16. Error distribution per window function. QP detector, Band A and reference signal 3.

FIGURE 17. Error distribution per window function. QP detector, Band B and reference signal 3.

FIGURE 18. Error distribution per window function. QP detector, Band C/D and reference signal 3.

C. Selectivity

The selectivity requirement corresponds to the frequency response a certain windowing function produces as an equivalent to the channel filter of the filter bank interpretation of the STFT. It is evaluated for sine-wave voltage stimulus, therefore, it can be drawn from the simulations done using the reference signal 1. In that sense, CISPR-16-1-1 gives limits for the selectivity for each band. For our analysis, we have established three critical amplitude decay points at -1.5 dB, -6 dB and -20 dB with respect to the peak injection level. The results for the selectivity evaluation of all window functions are in Fig. 19 to Fig. 21. The valid window responses are within the limits depicted as red dashed lines.

FIGURE 19. Frequency selectivity in CISPR Band A.

FIGURE 20. Frequency selectivity in CISPR Band B.

FIGURE 21. Frequency selectivity in CISPR Band C/D.

D. Interpolation factor

Interpolation of spectrum levels allows for estimating intermediate values within the STFT frequency discrete results. In our simulations, the impact of such interpolation was more important in the case of reference signal 1. The interpolation method used is the piecewise cubic hermite interpolating polynomial based on the Akima algorithm [26]. In all cases, the errors are calculated at the nearest neighbour of the injection frequency.

Fig. 22 shows the error distribution for the Parzen window in Band A and with the QP detector when the interpolation factor varies from 1 to 10.

FIGURE 22. Interpolation factor effect in error at injected frequencies for reference signal 1: Parzen window, QP detector and Band A.

It is noticeable how the error mean value and variability can be significantly reduced by increasing the interpolation factor. The behaviour is similar for all window functions, detectors and frequency bands.

V. EXPERIMENTAL VALIDATION

Metrological characterization of measuring receivers is a requirement of the international standard IEC/ISO 17025:2017 [27] for calibration and testing laboratories and the Annex K of standard CISPR 16-1-1 [2]. The current standardized calibration procedure is more tailored to the heterodyne receiver architecture, and it does not consider some specific problems of FFT-based measuring receivers. Due to the various architectures of measuring receivers, there are four core parameters that each receiver should satisfy to be compliant with [2]. These parameters are (i) sine-wave voltage level tolerance, (ii) frequency tuning accuracy, (iii) response to pulses and (iv) weighting detectors (selectivity). In [28] it was shown that testing of FFT-based measuring receivers for their conformity with the standard [2] in a metrology laboratory is currently more time-consuming and not properly supported by the standard compared to traditional swept-frequency systems and several practical calibration aspects were highlighted.

For the validation, two different oscilloscopes (i) Rohde & Schwarz RTO64 and (ii) PicoScope 5444D MSO were calibrated in an accredited calibration laboratory. Both instruments were controlled by the emiGO™ software so that they can be considered as FFT-based measuring

receivers. The results of the investigation from Chapter IV have been implemented in the said software: Kaiser-Bessel window with an overlapping factor $\alpha_f = 0.8$ and an interpolation factor of 10. The main parameters of both oscilloscopes are summarized in Table 5.

TABLE 5. Main parameters of tested FFT-based measuring receivers.

Oscilloscope model	Memory depth	ENOB	Bandwidth
R&S RTO64	500 MSa	8 - 16 bits	3 GHz
PS 5444D MSO	512 MSa	8 - 16 bits	200 MHz

Typical results of calibration of both instruments are summarized in Table 6 for one measurement channel and CISPR bands A, B, C (Picoscope 5444D) and A, B, C/D (Rohde & Schwarz RTO64), respectively. Due to the architecture of the receivers, a pulse-modulated continuous wave was used for the response to the pulse test. This approach is preferred considering limitation factors such as the memory depth of the oscilloscope (relative response to pulses with low repetition rates below 5 Hz), oscilloscope bandwidth (band C/D measurements) and vertical resolution (measurement of low emission levels). However, the FFT-based measuring receivers with an oscilloscope generally perform very well compared to traditional swept-frequency receivers and fulfil the requirements of [2].

TABLE 6. Calibration results of the receivers from Table 5. Legend: ¹R&S RTO64 oscilloscope, ²Picoscope 5444D MSO oscilloscope*.

Test / Tolerance	Max. error	Meas. uncertainty
Sine wave voltage level 66 dB μ V \pm 2 dB	¹ 0.12 dB ² 0.86 dB	¹ 0.09 dB ² 0.09 dB
Frequency tuning accuracy \pm 2 %	¹ 1×10^{-5} % ² 0.0006 %	¹ (0.009 to 300) Hz ² (0.009 to 300) Hz
Response to pulses (absolute) 66 dB μ V \pm 1.5 dB	¹ 0.40 dB ² 1.4 dB	¹ 0.50 dB ² 0.6 dB
Response to pulses (relative) Band A, \pm 2 dB, f_{rep} =2 Hz Band B, \pm 2 dB, f_{rep} =2 Hz Band C, \pm 1.5 dB, f_{rep} =10 Hz Band D, \pm 1 dB, f_{rep} =20 Hz	^{1,2} <0.11 dB ^{1,2} <0.75 dB ² <1.03 dB ¹ <0.29 dB	^{1,2} 0.50 dB ^{1,2} 0.90 dB ² 0.90 dB ¹ 0.50 dB
Frequency selectivity (-6 dB) Band A, \pm 20 Hz Band B, \pm 1 kHz Band C, \pm 20 kHz Band D, \pm 20 kHz	^{1,2} <0.10 Hz ^{1,2} <6 Hz ² <170 Hz ¹ <190 Hz	^{1,2} 0.71 Hz ^{1,2} 32 Hz ² 420 Hz ¹ 420 Hz

*Calibration results reported in the table above summarise the worst case from the results obtained for all detectors and oscilloscope channels.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

Tuning the spectral estimation parameters to minimize the uncertainty in electromagnetic emissions measurements made by FFT-based EMI receivers can be challenging. This is because no prior knowledge about the signal

characteristics is available. Also, one cannot make spectral estimation parameters configurable by the end users because a measuring receiver, as a measurement instrument, should be calibrated at certain conditions that ensure compliance with CISPR 16-1-1 and metrological traceability. This study made an extensive analysis based on numerical simulations to determine the suitable sets of spectral estimation parameters for direct sampling FFT-based measuring receivers. Such simulations, rising to a total of 489.6×10^3 iterations distributed in 1700 different digital implementations of the CISPR 16-1-1 measuring receiver, considered three reference signals that altogether are representative of electromagnetic disturbances: multitones, chirps, and broadband pulses. In that sense, the main outcomes of this work are wrapped up in what follows.

Table 7 gathers the outcomes per windowing function. There, symbols are used to represent the preferred window functions: (\surd) means a window is highly recommended, (\checkmark) is the window is suitable but not among the best, and (\times) translates into not recommended either because it is out of tolerance or because it is comparatively much worse than the typical window. The most satisfactory windowing functions in EMI the spectral estimation process are Chebishev, Nutall, Kaiser and Parzen, being the latter two the best in general. In that sense, it was found that the four windows fulfill the selectivity requirements and, overall, do not provide aberrant errors in the spectrum amplitude when tested for the different reference signals and CISPR bands.

TABLE 7. Qualitative summary of the window analysis results.

Windows	Selectivity			Accuracy										
	A	B	C/D	Multitone			Chirp			Rectpulse			Result	
				A	B	C/D	A	B	C/D	A	B	C/D		
Bartlett	\surd	\times	\checkmark	\surd	\times	\times	\surd	\surd	\surd	\surd	\surd	\surd	\times	\times
Mod Bartlett-Hanning	\surd	\surd	\checkmark	\times	\times	\times	\times	\times	\surd	\surd	\surd	\times	\times	\times
Blackman	\surd	\surd	\checkmark	\surd	\surd	\surd	\times	\times	\surd	\surd	\surd	\times	\times	\times
Blackman-Harris	\surd	\surd	\checkmark	\surd	\surd	\surd	\times	\times	\surd	\surd	\surd	\times	\times	\times
Bohman	\surd	\surd	\checkmark	\surd	\surd	\surd	\times	\times	\surd	\surd	\surd	\times	\times	\times
Chebyshev	\surd	\surd	\checkmark	\surd	\times	\times	\surd	\times	\surd	\surd	\surd	\surd	\times	\checkmark
Flat-Top	\surd	\surd	\checkmark	\surd	\times	\surd	\times	\times	\times	\times	\surd	\times	\times	\times
Gaussian	\surd	\surd	\checkmark	\times	\surd	\surd	\times	\times	\times	\times	\times	\times	\times	\times
Hamming	\surd	\surd	\checkmark	\times	\surd	\times	\times	\times	\surd	\surd	\surd	\times	\times	\times
Hann	\surd	\surd	\checkmark	\times	\times	\times	\times	\times	\surd	\surd	\surd	\times	\times	\times
Kaiser-Bessel	\surd	\surd	\checkmark	\surd	\surd	\surd	\surd	\times	\surd	\surd	\surd	\surd	\times	\surd
Nutall	\surd	\surd	\checkmark	\surd	\surd	\surd	\surd	\surd	\surd	\surd	\surd	\surd	\times	\surd
Parzen	\surd	\surd	\checkmark	\surd	\surd	\surd	\surd	\surd	\surd	\surd	\surd	\surd	\surd	\surd
Rectangular	\times	\times	\checkmark	\times	\times	\times	\times	\times	\times	\times	\surd	\times	\times	\times
Taylor	\times	\times	\times	\times	\times	\times	\times	\times	\times	\times	\times	\times	\times	\times
Tukey	\surd	\times	\checkmark	\surd	\times	\times	\times	\times	\times	\times	\times	\times	\times	\times
Triangular	\surd	\times	\checkmark	\surd	\times	\times	\surd	\times	\surd	\surd	\surd	\surd	\surd	\times

Also, for the said windowing functions, it is important to use an overlapping factor of at least 75 % in order to avoid large errors when dealing with impulsive signals. Moreover, even if it is out of the scope of the investigation, it is recommended not to increase the overlapping factor above 95 % as this may lead to a significant increase in computational time, making the spectral estimation extremely slow and memory-consuming.

Likewise, it is advised to use a frequency step of at least $1/4$ RBW with a minimum frequency interpolation factor between 5 and 10 to achieve a good trade-off between

frequency resolution, accuracy, and processing load. This combination of parameters has kept the scalloping loss low and an excellent detection of the peak levels for all weighting detectors.

Finally, the optimal parameters have been tested with real instrumentation using dedicated software to calculate the spectrum accordingly. The tests conducted in an accredited metrology laboratory delivered excellent results regarding the CISPR 16-1-1 standard requirements. This means the compliance of the measuring receiver implementation is confirmed by the maximum error and the measurement uncertainty obtained through the calibration for each relevant quantity as shown in Table 6.

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